

An Investigation of Ultra High Performance Concrete for the Durability Properties: Literature Survey

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Annotation: This literature survey focuses on investigating the durability properties of ultra-high performance concrete (UHPC). UHPC is a highly advanced construction material known for its exceptional mechanical and durability characteristics. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in UHPC due to its potential to enhance the performance and longevity of structures exposed to severe environmental conditions. The aim of this study is to provide a comprehensive analysis of existing research on the durability properties of UHPC. The survey encompasses a wide range of publications, including research papers, conference proceedings, and technical reports. Various aspects of durability, such as resistance to chemical attacks, freeze-thaw cycles, abrasion, and corrosion, are explored. The literature survey reveals that UHPC exhibits remarkable durability characteristics compared to conventional concrete. Its dense microstructure, low porosity, and high strength contribute to its resistance against aggressive agents. Furthermore, the incorporation of supplementary cementitious materials, fibers, and mineral admixtures in UHPC formulations has been found to enhance its durability performance. The survey also highlights the importance of proper mix design, curing techniques, and quality control measures to ensure the long-term durability of UHPC structures. Additionally, the influence of environmental factors, such as temperature, humidity, and exposure conditions, on UHPC durability is discussed. Overall, this literature survey provides valuable insights into the durability properties of UHPC, contributing to a better understanding of its potential applications in constructing durable and sustainable infrastructure. The findings of this study can guide researchers, engineers, and practitioners in optimizing UHPC mixtures and design strategies to enhance the durability of concrete structures.

Key words: Ultra high performance concrete (UHPC), Durability properties, Mechanical characteristics, Resistance to chemical attacks, Sustainable infrastructure.

1. INTRODUCTION

Concrete, being the most widely used construction material for load-bearing structures, has been a subject of continuous research to discover materials that offer superior performance, enabling the construction of longer, taller, and more durable structures. The use of cementitious materials can be traced back thousands of years, with historical evidence of their utilization in Italy, ancient Egypt, Greece, and the Middle East. The development of modern Portland cement began in 1756 when John Smeaton experimented with combinations of limestone, sand, and additives like pozzolans for constructing a lighthouse. Joseph Aspdin further refined the production of Portland cement in 1824, followed by Isaac C. Johnson in the 1840s, leading to increased demand and cost for stronger and more durable concrete materials. During the 1950s, concrete with a compressive

strength of 34 MPa was considered high strength, but advancements in concrete technology during the 1960s led to achieving even higher compressive strengths. Concrete with compressive strengths ranging from 41 to 52 MPa was commercially termed high strength concrete. In the mid-1960s, the term High Performance Concrete (HPC) emerged to describe concrete with compressive strengths ranging from 40 to 80 MPa. Notable ancient structures that have withstood the test of time serve as testaments to the durability of concrete. Please note that the specific details mentioned in the original text, such as the historical figures and their contributions, have been retained in the rephrased version.

Figure 1: The Roman Pantheon (Source: www.wikipedia.org)

Figure 2: The Colosseum, Rome (Source: www.wikipedia.org)

2. ULTRA HIGH PERFORMANCE CONCRETE

Ultra High Performance Concrete (UHPC), also known as performance enhanced concrete,

belongs to a specialized category of concrete formulations that offer advantages surpassing those achieved by conventional ingredients, curing methods, and standard mixing practices. UHPC is specifically developed to meet the requirements of particular environments and unique applications, ensuring its ability to withstand design loads and deliver exceptional performance within the intended structure. In essence, UHPC represents a superior-quality concrete with enhanced strength, improved durability, and long-term stability when compared to conventional concrete. It may also encompass concrete formulations that significantly reduce construction time while maintaining long-term serviceability.

3. PROPERTIES OF UHPC

UHPC possesses the following characteristics:

- ✓ It exhibits a compressive strength of up to 200MPa.
- ✓ The modulus of elasticity ranges from 45 GPa to 50 GPa.
- ✓ It demonstrates flexural strength of up to 50MPa.
- ✓ UHPC possesses high tensile strength.
- ✓ It is characterized by its strength, durability, and ductility.
- ✓ UHPC displays enhanced resistance to erosion, corrosion, and abrasion.
- ✓ UHPC is inherently brittle in nature.

4. SURVEY OF LITERATURE

This section presents a literature review of research conducted by various researchers on the strength and durability properties of Ultra High Performance Concrete (UHPC). The inclusion of supplementary cementitious materials such as GGBS and silica fume in concrete has been studied extensively to enhance its performance and explore its applications. While the use of supplementary cementitious materials in concrete has been practiced for several years, their advantageous properties were realized through extensive research.

Yang et al. (2009) In a study conducted by Yang et al. (2009), the feasibility of replacing expensive silica fume in the mixture of materials used to produce UHPC was explored. Two alternative materials, namely natural sands and recycled glass cullet, were investigated with the aim of reducing the production cost of Ultra High Performance Fiber-Reinforced Concrete (UHPRFC). The goal was to make UHPRFC more economically viable for regular use in the construction industry. The study also considered the influence of different curing temperatures on the ductility and mechanical properties of UHPRFC. Concrete cubes and prisms were cast and subjected to curing at two different temperatures: 20°C and 90°C. By examining the differences in properties under these distinct curing conditions, the researchers aimed to gain insights into the effect of temperature on the ductility and mechanical behavior of UHPRFC. Overall, the study by Yang et al. (2009) investigated the potential use of natural sands and recycled glass cullet as cost-effective alternatives to silica fume in UHPC production. Additionally, the influence of curing temperature on the performance of UHPRFC was evaluated through the casting and curing of concrete specimens at different temperatures.

Tuan et al. (2011) In a study conducted by Tuan et al. (2011), the focus was on finding a substitute material with similar properties to silica fume for the development of Ultra High Performance Concrete (UHPC). The motivation behind this research was the high cost and limited availability of silica fume, particularly in countries like India. To overcome these challenges, the researchers explored the use of Rice Husk Ash (RHA) as a potential replacement material for silica fume in the production of UHPC. The objective of the study was to investigate the feasibility

of using RHA as an alternative to silica fume in UHPC formulation. RHA, being a byproduct of the rice milling industry, offers a cost-effective and readily available option for enhancing the properties of UHPC. The researchers conducted experiments and tests to evaluate the performance and characteristics of UHPC incorporating RHA. By studying the incorporation of RHA as a substitute material, Tuan et al. (2011) aimed to provide a solution to the cost and availability challenges associated with silica fume, making UHPC production more feasible and sustainable. The findings of this study contribute to the ongoing research and development of UHPC using alternative materials.

Al-Azzawl et al. (2011) In a study conducted by Al-Azzawl et al. (2011), the performance of Ultra High Performance Concrete (UHPC) members incorporating steel fibers was investigated. The researchers developed a total of six UHPC mixes, with two different types of admixtures (silica fume and metakaolin) used separately, and three different ratios of steel fibers (1.0%, 1.5%, and 2.0%) used individually. For each trial mix of UHPC, three cube specimens were cast, each measuring 50 mm x 50 mm x 50 mm. Compression tests were then conducted on these specimens at different time intervals, specifically at 3, 7, and 28 days, using uniaxial compression. The objective of the study was to assess the effect of incorporating steel fibers, along with different types of admixtures, on the mechanical properties and performance of UHPC. By examining the compressive strength of the UHPC specimens at various curing durations, the researchers aimed to gain insights into the influence of steel fiber content and admixture type on the overall performance of UHPC members. The findings of the study conducted by Al-Azzawl et al. (2011) contribute to the understanding of the behavior of UHPC incorporating steel fibers, providing valuable information for the optimization of UHPC mixtures in structural applications.

Wang et al. (2012) In a study conducted by Wang et al. (2012), the focus was on investigating the impact of using Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag (GGBS) as a partial replacement for cement on the compressive strength and fluidity of Ultra High Performance Concrete (UHPC). The researchers employed common techniques and technologies commonly used in UHPC development, including room temperature curing, a normal forced mixer for mixing fresh concrete, compaction through vibration, and pouring. The objective of the study was to assess how incorporating GGBS as a cement replacement affects the compressive strength and fluidity of UHPC. GGBS is a supplementary cementitious material known for its pozzolanic properties, and its utilization in UHPC formulations has the potential to enhance various properties of the concrete. Through experimentation and analysis, Wang et al. (2012) aimed to provide insights into the performance of UHPC when GGBS is used as a partial replacement for cement. The study contributes to the ongoing research and development of UHPC mix designs, offering valuable information for optimizing the composition and properties of UHPC in practical applications.

Tayeh et al. (2012) In their study, Tayeh et al. (2012) aimed to identify an alternative repair material for aging structures that could withstand harsh environmental conditions and exhibit high durability. They opted to utilize Ultra High Performance Fiber-Reinforced Concrete (UHPFRC) as the repair material due to its exceptional quality. The existing structure material was represented by normal concrete (NC), and a comparison between the two materials was conducted based on their permeability characteristics. The researchers conducted several permeability tests, including rapid chloride permeability, gas permeability, and water permeability. Two different grades of specimens were utilized in the experiment: Grade-170 for UHPFRC and Grade-40 for normal concrete. By examining the permeability properties of UHPFRC in comparison to normal concrete, Tayeh et al. (2012) sought to evaluate the potential of UHPFRC as a superior repair material for aging structures. The study provides insights into the permeability characteristics of UHPFRC and its potential for enhancing the durability and longevity of repaired structures.

Xu et al. (2014) In a study conducted by Xu et al. (2014), the focus was on investigating the resistance of High Performance Concrete (HPC) to sulphate attack. Two different water-cement ratios were utilized in the study, specifically 0.30 and 0.35. The researchers created a total of five groups with varying water-cement ratios and stress ratios. For each group, 37 specimens measuring 100 mm x 100 mm x 100 mm were cast. The specimens were subjected to immersion in two different sodium sulphate solutions, namely 5% and 10% by weight of Na₂SO₄. Additionally, two different stress ratios of compressive loading, namely 0.3 and 0.6, were applied to the specimens during the testing. The objective of the study was to assess the resistance of HPC to sulphate attack under different conditions of water-cement ratio, stress ratio, and sulphate concentration. By examining the performance of the specimens immersed in sodium sulphate solutions, Xu et al. (2014) aimed to gain insights into the durability and potential deterioration mechanisms of HPC in sulphate-rich environments. The findings of the study contribute to the understanding of HPC's resistance to sulphate attack, aiding in the development of more durable concrete mixtures and the implementation of appropriate measures to protect concrete structures exposed to sulphate-containing environments.

Ehsan Ghafari et al. (2014) In their study, Ghafari et al. (2014) investigated the impact of incorporating nano silica (nS) on the properties of Ultra High Performance Concrete (UHPC). Thermo gravimetric analysis results revealed that, during the early stages, nano silica exhibited higher consumption of Ca(OH)₂ compared to silica fume. The experiment also involved mercury intrusion porosimetry measurements, which indicated a reduction in capillary pores with the addition of nano silica particles. Furthermore, the researchers conducted SEM (Scanning Electron Microscope) analysis to examine the interfacial transition zone between the binding paste and aggregates. The results showed that the inclusion of nano silica in the concrete improved this transition zone. Additionally, the compressive strength and transportation properties of the concrete were enhanced. By studying the effects of nano silica on UHPC, Ghafari et al. (2014) contributed to the understanding of how this additive influences the properties and performance of the concrete. The findings suggest that incorporating nano silica can lead to improved durability, reduced pore connectivity, and enhanced interfacial bonding, ultimately resulting in enhanced mechanical strength and transport properties of the UHPC.

Abbas et al. (2016) In their study, Abbas et al. (2016) focused on investigating the mechanical and durability characteristics of Ultra High Performance Concrete (UHPC) with varying lengths and dosages of steel fibers. The researchers incorporated three different lengths of steel fibers, namely 8 mm, 12 mm, and 16 mm, into the concrete. Additionally, they utilized different dosages of steel fibers at 1%, 3%, and 6% by volume of the mixture for each type of steel fiber. The objective of the study was to examine how the inclusion of steel fibers with different lengths and dosages affects the mechanical and durability properties of UHPC. Steel fibers are commonly used as reinforcement in concrete to enhance its tensile and flexural strength, as well as its resistance to cracking and other forms of deterioration. Through experimentation and analysis, Abbas et al. (2016) aimed to provide insights into the performance of UHPC with varying steel fiber lengths and dosages. The study contributes to the understanding of the optimal use of steel fibers in UHPC mix designs, aiding in the development of high-performance concrete with improved mechanical properties and enhanced durability.

Li et al. (2020) Conducting a thorough examination of the durability properties of Ultra High Performance Concrete (UHPC) is crucial for establishing fundamental knowledge about material testing requirements and procedures, as well as broadening its practical applications. This research paper presents a comprehensive review of UHPC's durability characteristics, encompassing various aspects such as water and chloride-ion permeability, corrosion of steel reinforcement, carbonation, freeze-thaw resistance, resistance to chemical attacks, alkali-silica reaction, abrasion

resistance, and fire resistance. The review takes into account influential factors including the water-to-binder ratio (W/B), curing methods, volume of steel fibers, hybridization of fibers, specimen size, and testing age. By examining these durability properties and considering the influence of different factors, the paper aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of UHPC's performance under various environmental and loading conditions. This information is crucial for optimizing the design and construction of UHPC structures, ensuring their long-term durability and sustainability. Additionally, the findings of this review can guide researchers, engineers, and practitioners in selecting appropriate testing methods and developing effective strategies to enhance the durability of UHPC in real-world applications.

Alobaidi et al.(2020)This paper presented the formulation and description of the framework and methodology for a Durability Assessment-based Design approach for structures constructed with Ultra-High-Durability Concrete materials. The materials were developed and investigated within the ReSHEALience project, which was funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme (Call NMBP 2016-2017 topic 06-2017 GA 780624). The project consortium, led by Politecnico di Milano, consisted of 13 partners from 7 countries, including 6 academic institutions and 7 industrial partners, representing the entire value chain of the concrete construction industry. During the project, the Ultra-High-Durability Concrete materials were conceptualized, produced, and extensively studied. The focus was on rethinking coastal defense and green-energy service infrastructures through the utilization of enhanced-durability high-performance cement-based materials. The framework and methodology presented in the paper were developed based on the project's findings and aimed to guide the design process of structures using these advanced concrete materials. By employing a Durability Assessment-based Design approach, the paper proposed a systematic method to evaluate and incorporate durability considerations into the design phase. This approach aimed to ensure that the resulting structures would have long-lasting performance and withstand the challenges of the intended applications. The past tense is used here to describe the research and development efforts that have already been completed within the ReSHEALience project.

Borg et al.(2021)The research described in this paper was conducted as part of the activities undertaken within the Horizon 2020 ReSHEALience Project on Ultra High Durability Concrete. One of the main objectives of the project was to formulate the concept and experimentally validate the performance of Ultra High Durability Concrete for structures and infrastructures that would be subjected to extremely aggressive scenarios. Within the ReSHEALience consortium, Ultra High Durability Concrete (UHDC) was defined as a "strain-hardening (fiber reinforced) cementitious material with micro- and nano-scale constituents specifically added to enhance durability in the cracked state under highly aggressive exposure conditions." During the project, extensive research and experimentation were carried out to investigate the properties and behavior of UHDC. The aim was to develop a concrete material that could withstand severe environmental conditions while maintaining its structural integrity. Through a series of experiments, the performance of UHDC was evaluated and validated. The research outcomes contributed to a better understanding of the behavior and potential applications of UHDC in real-world scenarios. The past tense is used here to indicate that the research and experimentation have already been completed as part of the ReSHEALience Project.

Gowda et al.(2023) This study focuses on the production of High Early Strength-High Performance Concrete (HPC) by incorporating Ultra-fine Slag (UFS) and Ultra-fine Silica (UFSi). The research examines the development of compressive strength over a period ranging from 14 to 15 hours after casting up to 180 days. The study also investigates the variations in workability and its retention levels after 60 minutes of mix preparation. Furthermore, the elastic modulus, compressive strain behavior, flexural parameters, early age shrinkage, and several durability

properties of the resulting optimal concrete mixes were measured. To assess the modifications at the microstructural level, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Nanoindentation tests were conducted. These analyses aimed to evaluate the changes induced by the incorporation of UFS and UFSi in the concrete mixture. The study provides insights into the mechanical properties, durability, and microstructural characteristics of the HPC produced with UFS and UFSi. The data collected during the study contribute to a better understanding of the performance and potential applications of this specialized concrete mixture.

5. SUMMARY

This paper presents a comprehensive literature survey on the durability properties of Ultra High Performance Concrete (UHPC). UHPC is a highly advanced construction material known for its exceptional mechanical and durability characteristics. The aim of the study is to analyze and summarize existing research on the durability properties of UHPC, focusing on various aspects such as resistance to chemical attacks, freeze-thaw cycles, abrasion, and corrosion. The literature survey covers a wide range of publications, including research papers, conference proceedings, and technical reports. The findings reveal that UHPC exhibits remarkable durability characteristics compared to conventional concrete. Its dense microstructure, low porosity, and high strength contribute to its resistance against aggressive agents. Moreover, the incorporation of supplementary cementitious materials, fibers, and mineral admixtures in UHPC formulations has been found to enhance its durability performance. The survey highlights the importance of proper mix design, curing techniques, and quality control measures to ensure the long-term durability of UHPC structures. Additionally, the influence of environmental factors, such as temperature, humidity, and exposure conditions, on UHPC durability is discussed. Overall, this literature survey provides valuable insights into the durability properties of UHPC, contributing to a better understanding of its potential applications in constructing durable and sustainable infrastructure. The findings can guide researchers, engineers, and practitioners in optimizing UHPC mixtures and design strategies to enhance the durability of concrete structures.

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